

Performance and farming analysis of sweet corn through implementing integrated plant management (IPM) In irrigation land, Jambi province (land optimization with pattern of rice-rice-secondary/horticultural plants)

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ABSTRACT

Tanjung Jabung Barat Regency is one of irrigated rice fields in Jambi Province that farmers applied generally cropping pattern of rice-rice-secondary/horticulture. Farmers usually cultivate sweet corn in rice field that are rather high with irrigation water management. The purpose of the assessment was to determine performance and the economic feasibility of sweet corn farming through the integrated plant management (IPM) in irrigated rice field. This assessment was conducted at dry season 2016 in Sri Agung Village Batang Asam sub District, Tanjung Jabung Barat District, Jambi Province using some components of sweet corn technology. The parameters observed were growth, sweet corn yield and financial analysis to determine the feasibility level of farming. The analysis used was analysis of acceptance, opinion, analysis of the balance of revenue on the cost (R/C). The plant performance showed good growth refer to plant height of 232.4 cm, leaf number of 13.5, leaf length of 96.6 cm, leaf width of 8.8 cm, cob height of 109.4 cm, stem diameter of 7.2 cm, 21.8 cm cob length, 20.5 cm cob diameter and 4.7 ounces of cob weight. The yield of 400 kg young corn and 6000 kg large corn per hectare gave revenue of IDR 25,400,000/ha. Sweet corn production cost was IDR 15,940,000/ha and the income was IDR 9,460,000/ha with the R/C ratio 1.59. This means that sweet corn is feasible to be applied to support the optimization of land with cropping pattern of rice-rice-secondary/horticulture in irrigated rice fields.

Key words: *Sweet corn, performance, economic feasibility, irrigated rice field*

INTODUCTION

Jambi Province with an area of 5.1 millions hectares (ha) consists of covering 2.65 millions ha dry land and 352,410 ha agricultural land for food crops. Based on the identification and characterization of AEZ, there are approximately 1,380,700 ha of dry land for agricultural land that are suitable for developing upland rice, maize and secondary crops, while the suitable land for rice crops is only 246,482 ha. Rice and secondary crops are important

commodities in Jambi Province so that they become a priority in supporting agricultural programs (Busyra et al. 2000).

Corn is one of the important food crops in Indonesia and is the second most important carbohydrate source after rice. Sweet corn is commonly cultivated and consumed by people in Indonesia. In Indonesia, the demand for sweet corn is very high, especially for direct consumption and the price is higher than other corn varieties. Sweet corn is a commodity that is worthy of being used as a superior commodity for food crops. Sweet corn is a very popular commodity especially by urban residents, because its delicious and sweet taste contains lots of carbohydrates, a little protein and fat. The prospect to develop sweet corn farming is very bright in order to increase the income and welfare of farmers, and the effective and efficient cultivation of sweet corn has the opportunity to provide high profits (Sudarsana, 2000). Characteristics of sweet corn are the seeds become wrinkled and useful as food ingredients, animal feed, fillers and other raw materials (Harizamrri, 2007).

Efforts to increase the production and productivity of national sweet corn are pursued through extensification, intensification, diversification and rehabilitation programs supported by the program of off-season sweet corn planting through applying suitable cropping patterns in an area. Efforts are being made to develop corn crops in several agro-ecosystems through an integrated crop management approach (ICM).

Production techniques applied consider the synergism that exists between these techniques in order to provide high results (Kartaatmadja and Fagi, 2000). Furthermore Hasanuddin (2004) that the production process through ICM which combines several technology components and production aspects that are synergized according to local conditions is believed to increase plant productivity efficiently so as to increase farmers' income. ICM aims to increase farmers' income through the technology application that is suitable for local conditions and can increase productivity and quality, and maintain environmental sustainability (Abdurrachman 2004). Corn plant is a plant that maximizes photosynthetic process and really need sunlight. So a good location for cultivating corn is an open area in the form of rice fields or fields that are not protected from sunlight. The location for cultivation of corn plants should not be flooded, but has sufficient water content.

One of lowland irrigated rice fields in Jambi Province is located in Tanjung Jabung Barat District. The general cropping patterns in rice fields is rice-rice-secondary/horticulture, meaning farmers can plant twice rice in both rainy and dry seasons and secondary crops in dry season. Sweet corn crops are usually farmers using rather high rice fields with the arrangement of irrigation water and planting can be done throughout the year. The purpose of the study

was to determine the performance and economic feasibility of sweet corn farming in irrigated rice fields.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was carried out in irrigated rice fields in Sri Agung Village, Batang Asam Subdistrict, Tanjung Jabung Barat District, Jambi Province in the dry season of 2016. Sri Agung Village is one of the transmigration settlement units located in the agricultural extension work area (AEWA) of Batang Asam Subdistrict, Tanjung Jabung Barat District of Jambi Province with an area of 1.288 ha including wet climate lowland rice field agro-ecosystem (LSDRIB) and is a division of Suban village. Geographically located at coordinates 010°1'18"-010°3'35" latitude south and 102°55'09"-102°57'46" East Longitude with altitude 10-15 m above sea level. The cultivation of land by farmers is designated as rice fields with an area of 1.75 ha/KK and yard with an average area of 0.25 ha per household. The yard is used as a housing and mixed garden while the business land is an irrigated rice field that is used for growing rice and secondary crops. Sweet corn The planting area of sweet corn was 1 ha with integrated crop management (ICM) approaches for sweet corn cultivation include soil tillage, qualified seeds use, superior varieties, planting system of *jajar legowo* 2:1, use of manure, dosage and method of fertilization, control pests. Sweet corn cultivation technology components through the integrated crop management (ICM) are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Technology components of sweet corn in irrigated rice fields
Sri Agung Village Batang Asam sub District-Jambi

Technology Component	Irrigated Rice Fields
Land preparation	Land cultivation
Superior varieties	Bonanza F1
How to plant	Tugal
Planting system	<i>Jajar legowo</i> 2:1 (spacing 30 x 50 x 100 cm),
Number of seeds/holes	1 seed
Fertilization (kg/ha)	
- Urea	300
- SP36	200
- KCl	100
Manure (kg/ha)	300
Biourine (l/ha)	60
OPT	IPM

Land preparation is done by land cultivation, making mounds and drainage channels around the plot. The 1 seed per hole was dibbled using planting system of *jajar legowo* 2:1 with a spacing of 30 x 50 x 100 cm (*legowo*

row planting system on corn plants is more directed at efforts to increase the acceptance of sunlight intensity on leaves and is expected the results of assimilation increase so that seed filling can be optimal).

In addition, it also facilitates the maintenance of plants, especially weeding both manually and with herbicides, fertilizing, and giving water. Manure of 300 kg/ha and liquid fertilizer of biourine 60 l/ha were applied. NPK fertilization dose was 300 kg/ha Urea + 200 kg/ha SP36 + 100 kg/ha KCl. Weeding is done twice, at 20-25 and 40-45 days after germination (DAG). Pest and disease control was carried out with integrated pest control (IPM).

Parameters observed consisted of growth percentage, plant performance, plant height, number of leaves, leaf length, leaf width, cob height, stem diameter, ear length, ear diameter and ear weight, yield of young corn (*janten*) and large corn. The growth data of corn plants were taken 10 plant samples and corn yield data is taken based on real results obtained per hectare.

While the farming analysis includes: 1) the use of production facilities, 2) the use of labor and 3) the level of farm efficiency done by financial analysis of the R/C ratio. Data analysis was performed with financial analysis to determine the level of feasibility of sweet corn farming. The analysis used is the analysis of revenue, income, analysis of revenue balance on costs (R/C) (Swastika, 2004; Malian, 2004) as follow.

Analysis of farm income:

Where :

π = Net farm income	(Rp/ha)
Y = Total production	(kg/ha)
Py = Price of selling soybeans	(Rp/kg)
Xi = Farm input input level	(Rp/ha)
Pxi = Farm input price	(Rp/kg)
BL = Other costs	(Rp/ha)

Farm feasibility (R/C)

Where :

R/C = Revenue and cost ratio
NPT = Total production value (Rp/ha)
BT = Value of total cost (Rp/ha)

Under the condition :

- R/C > 1, farming is economically profitable
- R/C = 1, economic farming is at a break-even point (BEP)
- R/C < 1, economic farming is not profitable (loss)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Location Characteristics

The land in Sri Agung Village has characteristics such as grey black to dark brown due to reduced organic matter, soil structure of crumbs, soil texture of sandy clays, low nutrients content, and slightly acidic soil (pH = 4.89). These soil conditions should be improved by applying ameliorants to optimize growth and yield. Application of organic matter such as manure/compost can provide essential nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium (Sanchez, 1976), improve soil physical properties and can bind excessive micro nutrients (Buckman and Brady 1982).

According to Anwar et al. (2007), that paddy fields cultivated for rice cultivation are classified as land suitability categories with S1 categories, which are very suitable for lowland rice and S3 category, that is marginal according to the availability of oxygen limiting factors so good drainage and additional inputs such as organic fertilizers and inorganic fertilizers are needed to obtain optimal productivity. Based on the results of soil analysis, some of the soil properties and optimal soil characteristics to support the growth of plants are pH between 5.5-6.5, clay soil texture, good drainage, 1:1 clay mineral type and material rich nutrients, moderate organic content, nutrient and micro nutrient availability (Makarim 2004). In general, the farming system that developed in Sri Agung Village was a food crop-based farming system with a cropping pattern: Padi-Padi-Secondary crops. Rice fields are usually planted in the rainy season, planting time at the beginning of the rainy season, that is, October/November and harvesting is carried out in January/February. In the dry season, rice planting time after the wet season rice harvest is January/February and harvest in May (Jumakir et al., 2014).

Figure 1. Pattern of rainfall in Sri Agung Village, Batang Asam Subdistrict, Tanjung Jabung Barat District, Jambi

The rainfall condition in Sri Agung Village is almost evenly distributed throughout the year with an average rainfall of 2,600 mm/year. The highest

monthly rainfall generally occurs in December/January and the lowest rainfall in August (Fig. 1, Table 2). Usually the rainy season in Sri Agung Village begins in September/October and the dry season in April/May. In Sri Agung Village, most of the farmers arranged the land as yard and irrigated rice fields

Table 2. Season calendar and cropping pattern in Sri Agung Village, Batang Asam Sub District Tanjung Jabung Barat District -Jambi

Variable	Month											
	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Season Calendar:												
- Wet Season (MH)												
- Dry Season (MK)												
Planting Pattern:												
- Rice												
- Rice												
- Secondary/Horticulture												

Growth and Sweet Corn Production

The performance of sweet corn plants in the vegetative phase and generative phase shows that the growth is quite good which refer to corn height of 232.4 cm, leaves number of 13.5, leaf length of 96.6 cm, leaf width of 8.8 cm, cob height of 109.4 cm, stem diameter of 7.2 cm, cob length of 21.8 cm, ear diameter of 20.5 cm and cobs weight of 4.7 ounces. Sweet corn yield for young corn (*janten*) and corn large was 400 kg/ha and 6,000 kg/ha, respectively (Table 3).

Table 3. Growth and production of sweet corn in irrigated rice fields of Sri Agung Village Batang Asam Subdistrict, West Tanjung Jabung District - Jambi

No	Parameter	Sweet Corn
1	Performance	
	-Vegetative	3
	-Generative	3
2	Plant height (cm)	232,40
3	Number of leaves (strands)	13,50
4	Leaf length (cm)	96,60
5	Leaf width (cm)	8,80
6	Cob length (cm)	109,40
7	Stem diameter (cm)	7,20
8	Cob length (cm)	21,80
9	Cob diameter (cm)	20,50
10	Weight of cob (ounces)	4,70
11	Productio of young corn/janten (kg/ha)	400
12	Production of large corn (kg/ha)	6.000

Performance: 1 = very good 3 = good 5 = medium

Analysis of sweet corn

The results of the analysis of sweet corn farming are listed in Table 4. From yield of 400 kg/ha young corn/*janten* and 6,000 kg/ha large corn can be obtained revenue of IDR 25,400,000 /ha. The production cost of sweet corn farming is IDR 15,940,000 /ha, with an income of IDR 9,460,000 /ha with a R/C ratio of 1.59. This shows that sweet corn farming is economically feasible to support the optimization of land by planting rice-rice-secondary/horticulture in irrigated rice fields.

Table 4. Analysis of sweet corn farming per hectare on irrigated rice fields in Sri Agung Village Batang Asam Subdistrict, West Tanjung Jabung District - Jambi

DESCRIPTION	Volume	Price (Rp)	Amount (Rp)
INPUT (Rp)			
I. Production Facilities			
- Seed	30 packs	125.000	3.750.000
- Urea	6 sacks (300 kg)	110.000	660.000
- SP 36	4 sacks (200 kg)	140.000	560.000
- NPK	2 sacks (100 kg)	135.000	270.000
- Manure	16 sacks (300 kg)	30.000	480.000
- Biourine	120 l	4000	480.000
- Herbicides	4 l	70.000	280.000
- Herbicides	8 l	60.000	480.000
- Insecticides	6 l	50.000	300.000
- Fungicides	8 l	60.000	480.000
Amount			7.740.000
II. Labor			
- Spray grass	wholesale	800.000	800.000
- Land cultivation	12 HOK	100.000	1.200.000
- Plant	12 HOK	100.000	1.200.000
- Fertilization	16 HOK	100.000	1.600.000
- Weeding	4 HOK	100.000	400.000
- Pest control	4 HOK	100.000	400.000
- Harvest young corn	wholesale	1.000.000	1.000.000
- Harvest large corn	wholesale	1.600.000	1.600.000
Amount			8.200.000
Total (I+II)			15.940.000
OUTPUT			
- Young corn yield (kg)	400	3.500	1.400.000
- Large corn yield (kg)	6.000	4.000	24.000.000
- Receipt (Rp)			25.400.000
- Income (Rp)			9.460.000
- R/C			1,59

CONCLUSIONS

The performance of sweet corn plants is quite good growth with yield of young corn (*janten*) and large corn is 400 kg/ha and 6,000 kg/ha, respectively. Sweet corn farming is feasible to be applied to support the optimization of land with the cropping pattern of rice-rice-secondary crops/horticulture in irrigated rice fields (R/C ratio 1.59).

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REFERENCES

- Abdurrachman, S. 2004. Teknologi budidaya padi tipe baru. Pelatihan Pengembangan VUTB. Sukamandi, 31 Maret-3 April 2004.
- Anwar, K., Suratman, dan A. Kasno. 2007. Identifikasi dan evaluasi potensi lahan untuk mendukung primatani di desa Sri Agung Kecamatan Tungkal Ulu Kabupaten Tanjung Jabung Barat Provinsi Jambi. Badan Penelitian dan Pengembangan Pertanian, Departemen Pertanian. Jakarta.
- Buckman, H.O. dan N.C. Brady. 1982. Ilmu Tanah. Bharata Karya Aksara. Jakarta.
- Busyra BS, N.Izhar, Mugiyanto, Lindawati dan Suharyon 2000. Karakterisasi zona agro ekologi (AEZ): Pedoman Pengembangan Pertanian di Provinsi Jambi. Instansi Penelitian dan Pengkajian Teknologi Pertanian Jambi. Badan Litbang Pertanian. Deptan.
- Derna, H. 2007. Jagung manis. Diakses di <http://www.scribd.com/doc/38158723/jagung-manis-No-4.pdf>, tanggal 18 September 2011.
- Harizamrry. 2007. Artikel jagung manis. Diakses di <http://harizamrry.com/2007/.../Tanaman-Jagung-Manis-Sweet-Corn>, Tanggal 7 Mei 2011.
- Hasanuddin A. 2004. Pengelolaan tanaman padi terpadu; suatu strategi pendekatan teknologi spesifik lokasi. Pelatihan Pengembangan Varietas unggul Tipe Baru dan VUTB lainnya, 31 Maret-3 April 2004. Balitpa. Sukamndi

- Jumakir, B. Julistia, Bustami, dan H. Hedi. 2014. Model pengembangan pertanian pedesaan melalui inovasi (mP3MI) berbasis tanaman padi pada agroekosistem sawah irigasi di Kabupaten Tanjung Jabung Barat Provinsi Jambi. Laporan Intern BPTP Jambi. Jambi.
- Kartaatmadja, S. dan A.M. Fagi. 2000. Pengelolaan tanaman teIDRadu konsep dan penerapan. Prosiding Simposium Penelitian Tanaman Pangan IV. Bogor
- Makarim, A.K. 2004. Teknik pengamatan, sampling dan analisis data untuk penelitian dan pengkajian VUTB. Balai Penelitian Tanaman padi Sukamandi. Sukamandi, Jawa Barat.
- Malian, A.H. 2004. Analisis ekonomi usahatani dan kelayakan finansial teknologi pada skala pengkajian. Makalah disajikan dalam Pelatihan Analisis Finansial dan Ekonomi bagi Pengembangan Sistem dan Usahatani Agribisnis Wilayah. Bogor, 29 Nov- 9 Des 2004.
- Purwono, M.S. dan R. Hartono. 2005. Bertanam jagung unggul. Penebar Swadaya. Bogor.
- Sanchez, P.A. 1976. Properties and Management of Soil in the Tropic. John Wiley and Sons, Inc. New York.
- Sudarsana, N.K. 2000. Pengaruh efektivitas mikroorganisme-4 (EM-4) dan kompos terhadap produksi jagung manis (*Zea mays saccharata Sturt*) pada tanah entisol. diakses di : <http://www.unmul.ac.id/dat/pub/frontir/sudarsana.pdf>, tanggal 7 Mei 2011.
- Swastika, D.K.S. 2004. Beberapa teknik analisa dalam penelitian dan pengkajian teknologi pertanian. *Jurnal Pengkajian dan Pengembangan Teknologi Pertanian* 7(1): 90-109.